

8T – The Sphere Shape of Stars

O Manor

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Abstract:

By analyzing the primordial equation from an angle of probability, that is by associating each prime a certain parameter, it is possible to reason for the similar, sphere shape of stars. That is by assuming that the net curvature probability of occurrence is the same in all directions, and thus in 1-D it's a circle of equal probability and in three dimension it is a sphere. The shape of a sphere is a result of invariance in direction of net curvature propagation.

Introduction

First, we can represent the original equation, which regard Bosonic fields to be net curvature on the varying Lorentz manifold. Those Bosons are isomorphic to prime numbers or one - $\mathbb{P} \cup (+1)$, and propagating from matter clusters destabilized by the majestic (3), which is the electron, from the second element and above.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1)$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (1.1)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \quad (1.2)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1):(24 + (3)) + 3:(120 + (3)) + 5:(840 + (3)) + 7... \quad (1.21)$$

In recent paper we have presented a new representation of equations (1) and (1.1). That is by associating each prime curvature a certain probability $P(A) < 1$ of occurrence as presented in equations (2.1) and (3).

$$N_V = (+3) \rightarrow P(A) \quad (2)$$

$$P(A) < 1$$

We assumed same probability of propagation for all net curvatures of distinct amount. That is all net curvature has the same (A), for means of simplicity. Now the primorial is presented as equation (2.1) or equation (3) ignoring the constants.

$$P_A\# = \left(K * \prod_{A=3}^{A=2n+1} P(A) + \mathcal{M} \right) + P(A) \quad (2.1)$$

Let $A \rightarrow \infty$

$$P_A\# = \left(K * \prod_{A=3}^{A=2n+1} P(A) \right) \rightarrow 0 \quad (3)$$

In the context of the shape of a star we can try and provide an explanation using equations (2.1) and (3). Since the probability is not known, and the direction of propagation of net curvature, i.e. boson is not known, we can assume that each segment of the matric tensor in one dimension will have the same probability of net curvature reaching to it from a certain fermion entity. In other words, bosons can propagate to all directions without any laws in equal probability. Boson propagation means fermion clustering in larger and larger amounts as presented by delta function. arbitrary variations vanish in even number represented in the equations

$$\delta g \neq 0 \quad at \quad t = Q(t) \quad (3.1)$$

$$\delta g = 0 \quad at \quad t = Q(t + \Delta t) \quad (3.11)$$

There is always a chance net curvature will appear at later continuation of time. That is bosonic fields given by the primorial coupling series represented in (3.12):

$$\delta g = 0 \quad at \quad t = Q(t + \Delta t) \quad (3.11)$$

$$\delta g \neq 0 \quad at \quad t = Q(t + \Delta t) \quad (3.12)$$

$$\Delta t \rightarrow 0$$

$$\delta g = N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i \geq 0$$

Since we have $N_V = P(A)$ the probability of net curvature to appear from matter cluster in a certain direction is the same for all directions, and thus the result in one dimension is a circle.

Take three dimensional matrix tensor and the result is a sphere. The conclusion if one is correct is the following. Because the probability of emission is unknown to all directions, it means it is equal to all direction or invariant to directions. In one dimension, it is a circle which the center represents the fermion which the net curvature is propagating, and in three dimensions it is a sphere. We can state the idea in simple and elegant fashion: The sphere shape of a star is due to invariance to the direction of the net curvature propagation – i.e. bosonic fields causing fermion to cluster.

References

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- [3] O. Manor. "8T – The Coupling Constants Series and Probability" In: (2021)